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AND MIGRANT CHILDREN

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Summary

This paper is the first of a series of four policy brief deliverables. The main aim of these policy briefs is to report on the progress of IMMERSE project with respect to policy recommendations. This paper has been issued at a very early stage of IMMERSE. For this reason, we are offering an overview of the main findings obtained so far, together with some incipient policy implications

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Measuring immigrant children integration

OUTCOMES AND STAKEHOLDERS

1 Summary

This paper is the first of a series of four policy brief deliverables. The main aim of these policy briefs is to report on the progress of IMMERSE project with respect to policy recommendations. This paper has been issued at a very early stage of IMMERSE. For this reason, we are offering an overview of the main findings obtained so far, together with some incipient policy implications.

This document is split into four parts. The first section offers some information about the figures of migrant children in Europe and describes the main challenges for their integration. Secondly, we highlight the importance of school and intercultural education for the integration of migrant children; in addition, five main integration outcomes are defined. Next section deals with three policy implications: the development of a series of integration indicators on the basis of the five integration outcomes; the need of using a systemic approach involving all kinds of stakeholders; and the necessary interaction among outcomes. The concluding sections draws our preliminary findings related to policy implications, that mainly deal with the need of revisiting and resystematizing the current model of integration in a more comprehensive way, and getting the involvement of all relevant stakeholders.

2 Context and data on migrant children integration

Between 2013 and 2017, almost 2 million non-EU citizens took up residence in the EU-28 on a yearly basis (EUROSTAT, 2019). Among them, 20% approximately are children, many of whom are unaccompanied or separated from their families. One of the **most fundamental challenges** lying ahead for the EU consists of the **successful integration** of these recent arrivals, as well as of longer-established migrant populations, and their descendants.

In total, more than 38 million people born in non-EU-28 countries are currently living in the European Union, representing **7.5% of the population in Europe**. In addition, 21.8 million, 4.25% of the population had been born in a different EU Member State. In countries such as France, United Kingdom, Netherlands, Belgium, Germany and Spain migrants and their descendants already made up to 15% of the population (EUROSTAT, 2019). In 2015, almost one in four 15-year-old students in EU countries was either foreign-born or had at least one foreign-born parent (OECD, 2018).

According to the European Commission (2005) **integration** should be understood as a **two-way process** based on mutual rights and corresponding obligations of legally resident third country nationals and the host society which provides for full participation of the immigrant.

In the case of **children in immigration contexts**, there are a series of **specific barriers** and difficulties that need to be dealt with (cumulative losses as a result of migration, acculturation processes, dynamics of discrimination, social exclusion...).

In fact, the increased and diversified flows of recent years are putting national and regional administrations under pressure and have exposed gaps and shortcomings in the protection and support of all categories of migrant children. National education systems are the most impacted by this situation since they need to embrace growing cultural, linguistic, socio-economic and ethnic diversity. The growing number of children arriving in recent years is leading to a **re-examination of how best to integrate them successfully**. This is not only as a necessary step for the fulfilment of international obligations, but also particularly important considering that most of these young migrants will likely permanently settle in their country of destination.

3 Evidenced-based observations

3.1 Critical issues identified

Historically, **schools** have been the “**great equalizer**”, enabling students from diverse backgrounds, neighbourhoods, and income levels and young immigrants to have the opportunity for success (Clauss-Ehlers, Serpell, & Weist, 2013).

During the 20th century, the educational discipline and practice have undergone a significant transformation of the dominant models or responses to diversity (Wulf, 2003). In this respect, Intercultural education brings together in practice the principles of **interculturalism** and **inclusive schools** in order to realize the full potential of all students, including migrant and native children (UNESCO, 2018).

Intercultural Education aims to achieve a developing and sustainable way of living together in multicultural societies through the creation of mutual understanding, respect for and dialogue between the different cultural groups (UNESCO, 2006, 2010).

The principles of intercultural education (UNESCO, 2006)

- (1) Respecting the cultural of the learner through the provision of culturally appropriate and responsive quality education for all
- (2) Providing every learner with the cultural knowledge, attitudes and skills necessary to achieve active and full participation in society
- (3) Providing cultural knowledge and skills that enable them to contribute to respect, understanding and solidarity among individuals, ethnic, social, cultural and religious groups and nations

3.2 Methodology and main outcomes

Integration is a **complex process** that involves different aspects of human experience. Several authors have conceptualized the **different dimensions** or domains that are part of that process.

These dimensions are composed of **indicators**¹ and allow measure the degree of an individual's

¹ An indicator is an instrument that serves to observe what is essential about those objectives and goals, as well as about the process leading to them, which is complex and we cannot directly observe.

integration. IMMERSE main ambition is to develop a dashboard of integration indicators for immigrant children.

Main goals of IMMERSE indicators framework:

- 1 That migrant (and other) children reach their full potential in the most relevant **outcomes**
- 2 That migrant (and other) children, as well as their families, become an accepted part of society with **fully recognized membership** at the formal and informal levels.
- 3 The **responsibility** for integration goals rests **with all actors involved**: migrants themselves, the host government and institutions, and native communities.

Children integration involves five types of **outcomes**:

- **Legal status:** The satisfaction of basic needs, as well as the margin for vital possibilities and personal development depend, in the first place, on the degree of recognition and guarantee of their legal status and of the social rights attached to it (García Cívico, 2010).
- **Language:** As the medium of communication in any human society, the capacity to communicate in the national language of the receiving society is a precondition for full participation in society and full development of the person's potential
- **Psycho-social well-being and health:** Health and psychosocial well-being are primary outcomes that determine cognitive and behavioural capacities, and that are particularly determinant during childhood and adolescence (Barnett & Belfiel, 2006). Mental health in immigrants is determined by factors related to (1) the society of origin (2) the migration process, and (3) host society (World Health Organisation, 2004).
- **Social relations:** Social networks consist of the structural connections—the presence or absence of links—among individuals or groups. Social networks are very important in promoting migrants integration. They provide practical support –assistance in accessing rights and services- but also material and emotional support (Spicer, 2008).
- **Educational achievement.** Educational achievements foster the further employability and economic growth not just in the benefit of the migrant family but also of broad communities and society. Thus, the provision of quality education for migrant children with successful results translates in an increase of social cohesion and economic and social development in host countries (Ager & Strang, 2004).

All outcomes are highly interconnected and interrelated, and the section helps map the complex relations of dependency among them. In addition, there are **individual and situational factors** that affect their realization (**barriers and facilitators**).

Barriers and facilitators can be observed at **different settings** within the social system.

- 1 **Micro:** the child and his/her family
- 2 **Meso:** school, neighbourhood and other primary places in their daily life, including all possible relations at this “local” level (e.g. associations, social services, etc.).
- 3 **Macro:** the policies and large political, economic and social systems of a given society. This includes the vertical dimension of policymaking, that is, the relationship between the national, regional, and local levels (Penninx & Garcés-Mascreñas, 2016).

4 Policy implications

4.1 Developing new integration indicators

The need of improving integration of migrant background children has arisen the need of better understanding its underlying factors. In this respect, IMMERSE aims to **elaborate a dashboard of indicators** related to refugee and migrant children integration in schools and other experiential environments.

4.2 Using a systemic approach

The indicator production process **involves all relevant stakeholders** at the three proposed levels of analysis, with the aim of incorporating their insights and perspectives in a child right based approach. Table 1 shows this process.

Outcomes		Legal status	Language	Well-being	Social relations	Educational achievement
Barriers + facilitators						
Micro	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individual • Family 					
Meso	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • School • Neighbourhood • Social fabric 					
Macro	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local • Regional • National 					

Indeed, the use of the systemic approach

- responds to a **child-centered perspective** in terms of levels of proximity to the child
- Identifies the **relevant levels of intervention** regarding
 - Relevant stakeholders
 - Policy recommendations
- Allows **applicability and comparability** among countries

4.3 Interactions among indicators

In this approach, outcomes are **most often found at the micro level** (children outcomes) although they can then be aggregated into the meso level (school, neighbourhood and local) as well as into the macro level (regions and national level).

But some specific outcomes are **also found at the meso and macro level** (e.g. presence of conflict in terms of bullying at schools or generally episodes of discrimination and/or hate attacks at local, regional or national levels).

However, **the relevant determinants for all of these outcomes are found across all three levels**: at the micro level, both individual factors (within-child factors) and situational factors (mostly related to family), and the rest of situational factors are found at the meso and macro levels. Some of the determinants are shared across relevant outcomes, which means this information is particularly relevant to be included among the selected indicators, also from the point of view of data efficiency.

5 Conclusions

One of the **biggest challenges** currently facing the EU is the **successful integration** of 2 million non-EU citizens, 20% of whom are children. In the case of **children in immigration contexts**, there are a series of specific barriers and difficulties that are leading to **revisit successful parameters** of integration.

Historically, schools have enabled students from diverse economic, social or ethnic backgrounds to have the opportunity for success. In this respect, **Intercultural education** turns out to be the successful paradigm when aiming to achieve a developing and sustainable way of living together in multicultural societies.

Nevertheless, integration is a complex process that is conceptualized through different dimensions. Indeed, **Children integration** involves **five types of outcomes**: (1) legal status (2) Language (3) Psycho-social well-being and health (4) Social relations and (5) Educational achievement.

All outcomes are interconnected and interrelated and, in turn, influenced by **individual and situational factors**. These factors can be split into three levels, (1) Micro, the child and his/her family (2) Meso, school, neighbourhood and other primary places and (3) Macro, the policies and large political, economic and social systems.

In terms of **policy implications**, the first analysis extracted from the early phases of the research can be synthesised as follows:

- to strengthen the definition of an **appropriate and uniform model of integration** in European countries, without making standardisation prevail over flexibility and adherence to local needs
- to **connect and align all institutions/stakeholders** involved in reception and integration
- to **systematize the specific measures** for distinct target groups expressing differentiated needs, (such as UAMs, second and third generation migrants, minors from mixed families etc)
- to **align integration policies** with social, educational, urban and economic policies at the national level
- to promote measures **strengthening** the social **participation of children and young people**